

Quantum and Classical Statistical Systems in Terms of Constraints

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Classical statistical mechanics/thermodynamics is sometimes portrayed as an approximate approach to describing the classical mechanical motion of very large numbers of particles. Equilibrium statistical mechanics/thermodynamics, however, is a special situation in which thermodynamic averages such as temperature, pressure etc do not change in time. We argue in this note that this is due to constraints imposed on such equilibrium scenarios namely time reversal reaction balance. It is this (approximate) constraint which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which in turn defines average values of classical values e.g. pressure resulting from an average of bv ($b=\text{constant}$) and temperature being related to average kinetic energy. Interestingly, average values such as average energy and pressure may yield a classical mechanical relationship for adiabatic processes, otherwise the more complicated $dE=TdS - PdV$ applies to these averages. (To be more accurate one may use the constraints of microcanonical theory.)

Quantum mechanics is also a statistical theory because a single particle with a fixed momentum is characterized by a physical wavelength region and a probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$. If interactions occur with potential regions a superposition of these distributions (i.e. a momentum superposition) occurs i.e. $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This represents one constraint in quantum mechanics), but there is a second, namely that averages for a bound system match classical values. Thus, like classical statistical mechanics one may imagine a system characterized by a parameter say L (box length) which changes such that the particle stays in the same quantum state (i.e. an adiabatic change). Given that bound quantum mechanics is constrained to behave on average as a classical system it is not surprising that a $dE=PdV$ which is essentially a Newton's second law statement $dE=Fdx$ and is not necessarily linked to a usual statistical system. If a quantum state has its parameter changed nonadiabatically it should be able to have it change into a superposition of new quantum states (new L) which is very different from the classical statistical mechanical scenario. Furthermore the ideal gas relationship $PV=NRT$ and $E=3/2NRT$ (3 degrees of freedom) or $PV=(2/3)E$ matches a classical mechanical result because a particle with p may bounce from a wall yielding an impulse.

In this note we try to examine some of these underlying constraints and argue that even $dE=PdV$ for average E and P values (i.e. no entropy change) one must be aware of the specific constraints involved. In other words because $dE=PdV$ for both adiabatic classical statistical mechanical systems and a quantum eigenstate, these do not necessarily represent the same statistical type of physics. We further argue that quantum mechanical bound states are constrained to have some average and rms values such as $KE(x)$ and p rms behave as classical values and so these should not be taken to represent "intrinsic" quantum behaviour while average spatial density on the other hand does. (It is linked to the constraint of wavelength.)

Classical Mechanics and Statistical Mechanics

It is sometimes said that statistical mechanics/thermodynamics is an approach of dealing with classical mechanical equations for a very large number of particles. Classical particles, however, change in time (due to acceleration or collisions), but thermodynamical ones such as average energy, pressure and the number of particles with a particular energy e_i should not change in time in an equilibrium scenario. Thus equilibrium seems to be a constrained system of large numbers of particles obeying classical mechanics.

The question becomes: What is the constraint? We have argued in previous notes that although a microcanonical constraint scenario is fully accurate one may think in terms of a different, approximate constraint. This constraint ensures that for any given elastic collision of two particles, the time reversed reaction has the same probability i.e. for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$.

The constraint leads to special values of $f(e_i)$ which in turn are used to calculate thermodynamical averages (which usually do not change in time in equilibrium) such as energy, pressure, temperature etc. It is then interesting to find equations which govern the behaviour of these averages. These equations do not need to look like classical mechanical ones because average quantities based on special constraints are being examined. In fact: $dE = TdS - PdV$ shows that one does not have a classical mechanical situation unless $dS = 0$. In such a case $dE = -PdV$ is equivalent to $dE = Fdx$ which does not apply to a statistical situation.

Quantum Mechanical Constraints

Quantum mechanics of bound systems we argue is also a statistical theory based on constraints. First, a quantum particle has a wavelength and a spatial probability associated with this length, namely $\exp(ipx)$. This is a constraint which does not appear in classical mechanics. A constant p holds within the entire wavelength region, but the particle might be at different positions so the equation distance = velocity * time does not hold i.e. there is nonlocality. In such a case it does make sense to use time for a bound system because there are a range of values within a wavelength and this length is comparable to the system length. In fact for a forward moving particle in this probability scenario there is such a large time range that it overlaps with the time range of the particle moving backwards. As a result one distinguishes momentum probability only throughout space i.e. has orthonormal functions $\exp(ipx)$ and interference.

A quantum particle has momentum and so may impart impulses, but it does so in an unusual way due to the $\exp(ipx)$ spatial probability distribution.

The second constraint is that on average a quantum particle must yield classical values for kinetic energy as a function of x i.e.

$$[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}] = KE(x) \text{ classical } ((1))$$

((1)) must hold because quantum mechanics uses $V(x)$ which we argue is also a classical average consisting of: $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ with $V_k \exp(ikx)$ yielding an impulse hit which changes momentum by k .

It is important to note that the two constraints, especially the second because what may seem like intrinsic quantum behaviour is really due to the “classical” constraint on $KE(x)$ and p rms. The quantum constraints

A Wavelength and superposition

B Average kinetic energy = classical kinetic energy

lead to the nonclassical result of spatial density humps. For example, for a classical gas in a box spatial density is constant. For a single particle with fixed velocity in a box, the time it spends in each dx is constant. For a constant p quantum particle in a box with infinite walls, this is not the case. There is a spatial density linked to the time the particle spends in each dx i.e. its probability to be in each dx .

In general a classical particle bouncing back and forth in a box is not considered to be a statistical system.

Quantum Mechanics and the Ideal Gas

The classical ideal gas law for particles with momentum degrees of freedom:

A. $PV = NRT$ ((2a)) and B. $E = 3/2 NRT$ ((2b))

Using $T = dE/dS$ from thermodynamics yields:

$$S - S_0 = NR \frac{2}{3} \ln(E) - NR \frac{2}{3} \ln(E_0) \quad ((3))$$

And one also has: $PV = (\frac{2}{3}) E$ ((4))

((4)) holds for average quantities in a classical gas, however, this equation matches the classical mechanical result linking $E = .5mv^2$ and pressure = Force/Area. In other words the presence of ((4)) does not necessarily mean one has a statistical system. Given that a quantum mechanical bound state's average kinetic energy matches the classical results it is expected that velocity rms behaves like classical velocity. ((4)) follows for a quantum particle with fixed p in an infinite potential well as a result of classical mechanics and not statistical mechanics. This result holds even for a single quantum particle in the infinite well potential, but only for rms values e.g. p_{ave} .

The rms result follows from all possible $\exp(ipx)$ values (which exist both outside the L region and inside superposing to create $W(x)=0$ outside the box and $\sin(p_{ave} x)$ inside). Furthermore a spatial density of $\sin(p_{ave} x) \sin(p_{ave} x) CC$ (C = normalization) is created so this is not the constant spatial density classical gas scenario.

If one has many quantum particles (noninteracting) in an infinite potential well, one may take averages and observe ideal gas behaviour (i.e. classical mechanical behaviour) at the rms level because each particle at this level mimics a classical particle with the exception of spatial energy density. (In addition, there is the Pauli exclusion principle and the boson scattering enhancement effect in place, but under certain conditions (e.g. high T or low densities) one may

come close to the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario. Again the spatial density quantum profile is an issue unless one has high energy levels for which π is high so that $\sin(\pi x)$'s envelope is a horizontal line with the troughs hardly being resolved.

As a result, if one considers many quantum particles in a box with infinite walls one may use the microcanonical constraint to create level filling scenarios (say for a Maxwell-Boltzmann or fermion) case. From this one may obtain $f(e_i)$. Alternatively (and approximately) one may use the time reversal reaction balance constraint for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein scenarios for $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \text{ (MB) or } f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1-f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)]$$

$$\text{FD(-) BE(+)} \quad ((5))$$

Comparison of Quantum and Classical Statistical Mechanics

Classical statistical mechanics is said to have its basis in quantum mechanics, but quantum bound states are constrained to have an average kinetic energy which matches $KE(x)$ classical. Thus p rms behaves like a classical value although other factors are at play in the quantum system i.e. other constraints such as the wavelength etc. As a result it is possible to consider quantum rms values such as $KE(x)$ or p rms as having an “intrinsic” quantum nature when they are in fact completely classical due to the imposed constraint. Applying quantum rms results in such a manner to a classical statistical gas does not seem to mean these features are of a quantum mechanical origin. They are of a classical mechanical origin which is imposed on p rms of a quantum bound system.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that statistical equilibrium systems may be thought of in terms of constraints, not just in terms of probabilities. We further argue that one quantum constraint is that $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy) matches the classical value so that rms values such as p rms match classical results. As a consequence for a single quantum particle in a box $PV=RT$ with $E=3/2 RT$ holds, but this is equivalent to a classical particle for which $E=pp/2m$ and pressure may be linked to pp . There does not appear to be intrinsic quantum behaviour in this situation, rather one seems to see classical physics emerge through the constraint that $KE \text{ ave}(x) \text{ (quantum)} = KE \text{ (classical)}(x)$ for a bound state.

References

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